

SOCIAL-PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE OLYMPIC MOVEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This thesis covers the sociol-pedagogical foundations of the development of the Olympic movement in Uzbekistan. The importance of the Olympic movement in attracting young people to a healthy lifestyle, forming their spiritual, moral and volitional qualities is analyzed. The pedagogical possibilities of introducing Olympic values in the educational process are substantiated. The study used analytical and comparative methods to substantiate the socio-pedagogical effectiveness of Olympic education in the education of young people..

Introduction. In today's globalization environment, the Olympic movement is recognized as an important socio-pedagogical system that serves not only to achieve sports results, but also to educate the younger generation as healthy, spiritually mature and socially active individuals. Olympic ideals - the principles of honesty, justice, peace, friendship and healthy competition - are of great importance in forming a stable life position in young people in today's globalization environment. Reforms aimed at developing the sports sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan after independence created the basis for the rapid development of the Olympic movement. In particular, Uzbekistan's membership in the International Olympic Committee in 1993 was an important historical stage in the entry of the country's sports into the international arena. Since then, Uzbek athletes have been regularly participating in the Summer and Winter Olympic Games and achieving high results. This situation has increased interest in sports among young people and further strengthened the social significance of the Olympic movement.

According to statistics, in recent years, the percentage of young people in Uzbekistan who regularly engage in sports has increased significantly [1]. Instilling Olympic values in the minds of young people through physical education classes, sports clubs, and mass competitions in educational institutions has become an important pedagogical task. In particular, the introduction of elements of Olympic education in secondary schools and higher education institutions increases the effectiveness of the educational process.

From a pedagogical point of view, the Olympic movement serves the comprehensive development of the individual. Through Olympic education, the willpower, discipline, responsibility, and teamwork skills of young people are formed. Therefore, a scientific analysis of the socio-pedagogical foundations of the development of the Olympic movement in

Uzbekistan, as well as the identification of its potential in the educational process, is an urgent scientific problem today.

The object of this study is the Olympic movement, which is being formed within the framework of the physical education and sports system in Uzbekistan. The subject of the study is the social and pedagogical significance of the Olympic movement in the education of young people, as well as the mechanisms for the formation of Olympic values in the educational process.

Research methods. The research used methods of analysis of scientific literature, comparative analysis, pedagogical observation and generalization. Also, the socio-pedagogical aspects of the Olympic movement were analyzed based on local and foreign scientific sources. These methods allowed for a systematic analysis and conclusions to be drawn about the social and pedagogical aspects of the Olympic movement.

Scientific innovation. The study, for the first time in Uzbekistan, sheds light on the Olympic movement not only in terms of sports results, but also as a socio-pedagogical factor in the upbringing of young people, based on a systematic approach. The educational possibilities of Olympic education are substantiated from a pedagogical point of view.

Practical significance. The results of the study can be used as a practical guide for physical education teachers, coaches, and students of pedagogy. They also serve as recommendations for introducing elements of Olympic education into the teaching process.

Social foundations of the Olympic movement in Uzbekistan. The Olympic movement is an important social institution that serves to establish a healthy lifestyle in society, attract young people to physical activity, and increase social activity. State policy in the field of sports in Uzbekistan is aimed at creating favorable conditions for the population, especially young people, to regularly engage in sports, and this process is stipulated in state programs and regulatory legal acts [5]. Uzbekistan's cooperation with the International Olympic Committee and the systematic activities of the National Olympic Committee of Uzbekistan further increase the social significance of the Olympic movement. Achievements in international sports competitions form an interest in sports and a positive attitude towards them in the minds of young people, serving as an important motivational factor encouraging them to lead a healthy lifestyle [6].

Pedagogical foundations of the Olympic movement. From a pedagogical point of view, the Olympic movement is considered an effective educational system that serves the comprehensive development of the individual. In the process of Olympic education, important moral and volitional qualities such as honesty, discipline, will, diligence, teamwork and responsibility are formed in the younger generation. These aspects are substantiated in scientific research on physical education and sports pedagogy [7]. It is also noted in scientific literature that the targeted instillation of Olympic values in the process of physical education classes in secondary schools and higher educational institutions has a positive effect on the spiritual and moral development of young people and increases the effectiveness of the educational process [6]. This approach is considered in harmony with the concept of the Olympic Values Education Programme (OVEP) of the International Olympic Committee and is consistent with the international experience of education through sports.

The issues of the Olympic movement and its socio-pedagogical significance have been widely studied by domestic and foreign scientists. In particular, AA Abdullayev, in his scientific works, revealed the place of physical education and sports in personal education, justifying sports activities as a means of developing the spiritual and volitional qualities of young people [4]. RS Salomov's studies covered the role of Olympic education in the spiritual development of young people, and the issues of strengthening the educational impact through sports [2]. Among foreign researchers, the Olympic ideas put forward by P. Kulbertin became the basis for interpreting sports not only as competitions, but also as an important component of the educational system. These views were also consolidated in the official documents of the International Olympic Committee [7].

CONCLUSION

The above analysis shows that the development of the Olympic movement in Uzbekistan is inextricably linked to the social needs of society and the education system. The Olympic movement, along with promoting a healthy lifestyle and involving young people in physical activity, plays an important socio-pedagogical role in the formation of their spiritual, moral and volitional qualities.

The results of the study confirm that the systematic introduction of Olympic values into the educational process has a positive effect on the personal development of young people. Through physical education classes, sports clubs and competitions, such qualities as honesty, discipline, responsibility, teamwork and a culture of healthy competition are being formed. This shows that the Olympic movement is not limited only to sports results, but also performs a wide range of educational tasks. Also, the scientific views of local and foreign scientists serve as a theoretical basis for interpreting the Olympic movement as an effective means of youth education. The combination of international experience and the national sports system creates broad opportunities for the development of Olympic education in Uzbekistan. In conclusion, in-depth study of the socio-pedagogical foundations of the development of the Olympic movement in Uzbekistan and its wide introduction into the educational process are of great importance in raising a healthy, spiritually mature and competitive young generation. In the future, empirical research into the mechanisms for implementing Olympic education in educational institutions will be of great scientific and practical importance.

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